

Spectroscopic and Electrochemical Characterisation of some Complexes with Azamacrocyclic Ligands

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This work describes the synthesis and infrared, uv-visible, ¹H nmr and electrochemical characterisation of azacyclophanes and naphthalocyanines ligands and some Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes. The characterisation of some non commercial precursors of these compounds is also informed.

The results show that the ligands and complexes are essentially planar, their optical properties are similar to those found in phthalocyanines and some ligands stabilises Ni^I or Cu^I at potentials less than 1 V vs ESC. In order to increase the solubility of these systems in polar solvents, some alternatives to sulphonation are proposed.

During the last years many papers related to the synthesis, characterisation and various practical applications of complexes with macrocyclic ligands have appeared in the literature¹⁻³. The degree of insaturation and the size of the macrocycle has a marked effect on the chemical and photochemical properties and the stability of the oxidation state of the metallic ion⁴.

The metallic phthalocyanines are one of the most studied synthetic macrocyclic derivatives; they have been employed as catalysators, electrocatalysators, photoconductors, photosensibilisators, modified electrodes, photovoltaic materials, precursors of mixed valence and photocopy technology. On the other hand, macrocyclics similar to the azacyclophanes show catalytic activity in some processes related to the obtention of fuels and/or storage of energy^{1,5,6}. Hence, the reduction of carbon dioxide can be driven electrochemically⁷ in order to transform it into organic substrates that can be used as a cheap source of fuels and chemicals^{5,6}. In the reduction over metallic cathodes, the large overpotential required for driving electrode reactions at an appropriate rate is an unquestionable technical problem which has been addressed by adding some catalysts⁷. Recently, tetra-aza macrocyclic and related complexes of cobalt and nickel have been successfully used⁸.

Aza-macrocycles such as naphthalocyanines, derived from aromatic N-substituted heterocycles

Fig. 1. (a) Hexa-aza macrocyclic complexes derived from substituted phenanthroline (M = Ni, Cu); (b) naphthalocyanine complexes (M = Co, Zn).

and those derived from 1,10-phenanthrolines, with a similar structure but with a more extended π -electronic system, show the same or better possibilities than phthalocyanines. For example, some naphthalocyanines have been successfully employed as semiconductors and optical interrupter in laser radiation¹⁰. However, little is known about the properties of macrocyclic compounds derived from 1,10-phenanthroline and related bases and naphthalocyanines^{4,11}. Since these compounds can be considered relatives of the phthalocyanines and porphyrins, they have potentially interesting

chemical properties as catalysts in this kind of processes.

Scheme 1. Reaction scheme for the preparation of azacyclophanes.

Scheme 2. Reaction scheme for the preparation of naphthalocyanines (Refs. 14, 24, 29).

The synthesis and infrared, uv-visible, ¹H nmr and electrochemical characterisation of new complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} with macrocyclic ligands derived from azacyclophanes, synthesised from 1,10-phenanthroline and naphthalocyanines are informed in this work (Fig. 1). It is of particular interest to establish the nature of the redox processes and characterise the multiple electron transfers involving either or both the metal center and the ligand as in the case of the phthalocyanines¹². One additional goal of these preparations is the obtention of presently non-commercial ligands and its precursors in good yields.

Scheme 3. Reaction scheme for the preparation of polar solvent soluble azacyclophanes.

Results and Discussion

The compounds were synthesised as shown in Schemes 1 and 2. Elemental analysis of metal, carbon, nitrogen and hydrogen for the complexes are in agreement with a 1 : 1 metal to ligand stoichiometry within an error of 5%.

These azacyclophanes along with their metal complexes, are insoluble in conventional polar solvents. However, small variations in the synthesis of the macrocyclic could lead soluble ones¹³. In the case of the aza-cyclophanes, one of these modifications would consist of the use of precursors such as dichlorobipyrimidine and diammine-bipyrimidine, obtainable from 2,2',6,6'-bipyrimidine (Scheme 3)¹⁴. Crystal and molecular structure of some tin(IV) shows this ligand to be planar and bidentate¹⁵. This is an open area of synthesis.

Table 1 shows the ¹H nmr data and assignments for the hexa-azamacrocyclic (VIII), some of its

precursors (VI and VII) and the nickel(II) complex (IX). The analysis of the first and second order coupling and the use of double resonance techniques allows for the full assignment of the protons. Also, these spectra account for the purity of the samples as it is seen in Fig. 2. Full ^1H nmr assignments for precursors I–V have been published recently¹⁴. The importance of the precursors shown in Table 1 is associated with different possibilities of synthesising other derivatives¹⁴. In addition, they are not commercially available. Finally, it was not possible to take satisfactory ^1H nmr spectra of the naphthalocyanine complexes due to its paramagnetic character or low solubility.

TABLE 1— ^1H NMR DATA* OF SOME PRECURSORS AND MACROCYCLES

Compd. no.	H ₃ , H ₈	H ₅ , H ₆	H ₄ , H ₇	NH ₂
VI	7.66(d) (8.3)	7.84 (s)	8.22 (d) (8.3)	—
VII	6.92 (d) (8.7)	7.34 (s)	7.91 (d) (8.7)	5.97
VIII	6.87 (d) (8.0)	7.34 (s)	7.99 (d) (8.0)	—
IX	6.70 (d) (10.0)	7.48 (s)	8.00 (d) (10.0)	—

* Values in ppm from TMS; figures in parenthesis are coupling constants in Hz; (d) = doublet, (s) = singlet.

Infrared data were obtained in the 4 000–400 cm^{-1} region for the hexa-azamacrocyclic, some non-commercial precursors and the nickel(II) complex. Tentative assignments have been done by comparing their spectra to those of related compounds^{16,17}; the precursors exhibit the following important bands (T, stretching, δ , bending modes): I, μ_{CH_3} (T) 3 057, $\mu_{\text{C=N}}$ (T), 1 627, $\mu_{\text{C=C}}$ (T) 1 585, 1 529, $\mu_{\text{C-H}}$ (δ) 1 220 cm^{-1} ; II, μ_{CH_3} (T) 3 050, $\mu_{\text{C=O}}$ (T) 1 656, $\mu_{\text{C=N}}$ (T) 1 605, $\mu_{\text{C=C}}$ (T) 1 542, 1 501, 1 466, $\mu_{\text{C-H}}$ (δ) 1 129 cm^{-1} ; III, $\mu_{\text{C=N}}$ (T) 1 618, $\mu_{\text{C=C}}$ (T) 1 582, 1 552, 1 493, $\mu_{\text{C-H}}$ (δ) 1 139, 1 123, $\mu_{\text{C-Cl}}$ (T) 840 cm^{-1} ; IV, μ_{CH_3} (T) 3 050, $\mu_{\text{C=N}}$ (T) 1 632, $\mu_{\text{C=C}}$ (T) 1 581, 1 550, $\mu_{\text{C-H}}$ (δ) 1 230, $\mu_{\text{C-Cl}}$ (T) 854 cm^{-1} ; V, μ_{CH_3} (T) 3 057, $\mu_{\text{C=O}}$ (T) 1 657, $\mu_{\text{C=N}}$ (T) 1 608, $\mu_{\text{C=C}}$ (T) 1 539, 1 498, 1 458, $\mu_{\text{C-H}}$ (δ) 1 280, 1 132, $\mu_{\text{C-Cl}}$ (T) 845 cm^{-1} ; VI, $\mu_{\text{C=N}}$ (T) 1 618, $\mu_{\text{C=C}}$ (T) 1 579, 1 550, 1 479, $\mu_{\text{C-H}}$ (δ) 1 134,

1 114, $\mu_{\text{C-Cl}}$ (T) 852 cm^{-1} ; VII, μ_{NH} (T) 3 148, 2 917, $\mu_{\text{C=N}}$ (T) 1 624, $\mu_{\text{C=C}}$ (T) 1 574, 1 573, $\mu_{\text{C-H}}$ (δ) 1 282, 1 252 cm^{-1} .

Hexaaza-macrocyclic ligands and its complexes are systems that have 44 and 43 atoms respectively, being 124 and 123 their particular numbers of expected vibrational modes. This facts put difficulties to a full interpretation and their assignment. Nevertheless, it is possible to show the following tentative assignments for some representative modes: VIII, $\mu_{\text{C=N}}$ (T) 1 656, $\mu_{\text{C=C}}$ (T) 1 578, 1 502, $\mu_{\text{C-H}}$ (δ) 1 147, 1 104, 1 093 cm^{-1} . IX (Ni) $\mu_{\text{C=N}}$ (T) 1 620, $\mu_{\text{C=C}}$ (T) 1 559, 1 549, 1 506, $\mu_{\text{C-H}}$ (δ) 1 256, 1 221, 1 200, $\mu_{\text{Ni-N}}$ 425 cm^{-1} ; IX (Cu), $\mu_{\text{C=N}}$ (T) 1 617 $\mu_{\text{C=C}}$ (T) 1 556, 1 532, 1 491, $\mu_{\text{C-H}}$ (δ) 1 137, $\mu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ 435 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 2 ^1H nmr spectra of (a) 2,9-dichloro-1,10-phenanthroline (VI, CDCl_3); (b) 2,9-diamino-1,10-phenanthroline (VII, CD_3OD), (c) hexa-azamacrocyclic ligand (VIII, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{SO} + \text{CF}_3\text{CO}_2\text{D}$) and (d) Ni(HAMC), (IX, $\text{CD}_3)_2\text{SO}$).

These results exhibit the expected shifting to lower frequencies upon coordination on some macrocyclic ligand vibrational modes. The metal-to-

ligand vibrations appear in the expected range for these kind of complexes¹⁶.

Fig 3. Uv-visible spectra of (a) hexa-azamacrocyclo ligand (VIII, solid phase), (b) Ni(HAMC) (IX, solid phase), (c) Cu(HAMC) (IX, solid phase) and (d) Cu(HAMC) (IX, in *N,N'*-dimethylformamide)

On the other hand, complexes derived from naphthalocyanines have 81 atoms, a number corresponding to 237 normal modes of vibration. In this case, tentative assignments have been done by comparison to related porphyrine and phthalocyanine complexes^{16,18}: X (Co), $\mu_{C=N}$ (T) 1 630, 1 600, $\mu_{C=C}$ (T) 1 529, 1 506, 1 460, 1 435, μ_{C-H} (δ) 1 129, 1 097, 957, 948, 926, μ_{Co-N} 471 cm^{-1} , X (Zn), $\mu_{C=N}$ (T) 1 620, $\mu_{C=C}$ (T) 1 567, 1 466, 1 444, μ_{C-H} (δ) 1 152, 1 125, μ_{Zn-N} 441 cm^{-1}

It is possible to assign vibrations of specific groups to the following bands: (a) those appearing at ca. 1 360 and 1 080 cm^{-1} can be assigned to pyrrolic ring vibrations and (b) two intense bands at 875 and 730 cm^{-1} can be assigned to vibrations of benzene rings¹⁶. These last bands are also observed in the hexa-azamacrocyclic ligand and complexes.

Electronic spectra · The zinc and cobalt naphthalocyanine derivatives (X) show two very intense bands that could tentatively be assigned to *B* (Soret) and *Q* bands by comparison with those of the phthalocyanines and similar macrocycles with

porphyrine rings^{1,3,6}. Soret bands are located at 327–358 nm and *Q* bands 754–846 nm in these complexes.

Fig. 3 shows uv-visible spectra for the complexes and the hexa-azamacrocyclo ligand. These spectra do not show absorptions which can unequivocally be assigned to *Q* bands even in the free ligand. One reason for this could be related to the particular conjugation and tautomeric equilibria involved in this macrocycle¹⁹. The complexes show *d-d* bands typical of the planar complexes (Fig. 3).

Fig 4 Cyclic voltammograms (scan rate, 200 $mV s^{-1}$) of (—) hexa-azamacrocyclo ligand (---) Ni(HAMC) (IX), (· · ·) Cu(HAMC) (IX)

No substantial solvent effects were found in the electronic spectra of the complex of nickel(II), while that of copper(II) showed noticeable changes, for example, when it is dissolved in *N,N'*-dimethylformamide²¹, as seen in Fig. 3d. Similar experimental observations on related compounds have been reported elsewhere²² and were rationalised in terms of the molecular orbitals involved in the transitions²³.

Electrochemical data : In terms of the potential application catalysis, it is of particular interest to establish the nature of the redox processes by cyclic voltammetry and characterise the electron transfers involving either or both the metal center and the ligand as in the case of the phthalocyanines¹⁸. It must be noticed that the macrocyclic products of the

multiple reductions may have also important properties compared to those of the starting materials²⁴.

Fig. 4 shows the cyclic voltammograms of the slightly soluble hexa-azamacrocyclic and its nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes in the cathodic region. These results suggest the stabilisation of Ni^I and Cu^I species at -0.85 and -0.80 V vs SCE, respectively. Coulometric measurements indicate that these processes involve one-electron reduction. Furthermore, the absence of significant redox process for the free ligand in the region in which reduction happens (Fig. 4), suggests that the reduction process would probably occur on the metal centre.

The processes in both the metals appear to be different, as it is seen in Fig. 4. The copper complex does not show a clear anodic response while nickel complex exhibits a quasi-reversible behaviour with two anodic waves. Cyclic voltammograms for the nickel complex in the region from -1.5 to +0.1 V at different rates are shown in Fig. 5, where it is seen that they remain unchanged.

Fig. 5. Cyclic voltammograms for Ni(HAMC) (IX) in the range -1.5 to +0.1 V, at ν : 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9 and 1.0 V s⁻¹.

The synthesised naphthalocyanines were not soluble in these conditions. Attempts will be made in order to sulphonate these complexes in a similar way as it has been done for phthalocyanine derivatives²⁵.

Experimental

Synthetic methods for azacyclophanes were reported earlier by Ogawa^{19,26}; the cumbersome multistep synthesis produce the ligands with extremely low yield, i.e. < 1%. This synthetic pro-

blem has limited experimentation with these compounds to the determination of a few spectra^{25,27}.

Scheme 1 shows the reaction scheme for the high yield preparations and some of the experimental details found in our laboratories. Some modifications are related to the rigorous exclusion of moisture from the reactions and the use of separation chromatographic techniques. Commercial 1,10-phenanthroline was used without further purification. Methylation, oxidation to phenanthroline and chloration led to the obtention of 2,9-dichloro-1,10-phenanthroline; further ammonolysis brought 2,9-diamino-1,10-phenanthroline²⁸. Finally, through a condensation between 2,9-dichloro- and 2,9-diamino-1,10-phenanthroline, the hexaazamacrocyclic was obtained (Scheme 1)¹⁴. Scheme 1 also shows the synthesis for the nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes.

Cobalt(II) and zinc(II) naphthalocyanine were obtained through a modification of the reported synthetic routes^{24,29,30} (Scheme 2). It involved the previous synthesis of 2,3-dicyanonaphthalene or 2,3-naphthalenedicarboxylic acid.

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Bruker IFS-66V spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Karl-Zeiss DMR22 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Bruker AC-200P spectrometer in appropriate solvents at room temperature using TMS as an internal standard. Melting points were uncorrected. Cyclic voltammetry measurements were done in pre-treated nitrogen atmosphere in a PAR 172-175 instrument using a conventional three-electrode cell: glassy carbon, saturated calomel and platinum spiral wire as working, reference and auxiliary electrodes, respectively. The solvent was *N,N'*-dimethylformamide and the supporting electrolyte tetraethylammonium perchlorate. The voltammograms were recorded on a X-Y Huston-Omnigraphic 2000 X-Y recorder, connected to a PAR 174 potentiostat. Potential limits were selected through a PAR 175 universal programmer. Controlled potential electrolysis was done by using the former potentiostat and a PAR 179 digital coulometer.

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